

**КАРТОШКА УРУҒЧИЛИГИДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ БИОТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРНИНГ
ИЛМИЙ-УСЛУБИЙ ВА НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ**

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Аннотация. Мақолада картошка уруғчилигида замонавий биотехнологиялардан фойдаланишнинг илмий-услубий ва назарий асослари ёритилган. Замонавий биотехнологик усуллар ёрдамида вируслардан ҳоли ҳамда турли иқлим омилларига мослашувчан янги картошка навларини яратиш бўйича олиб борилаётган илмий ёндашувлар ўрганиб чиқилган. Генетик-селекция, молекуляр маркерлаш, ўсимлик тўқима култураси, монодурагай, микробиологик, экологик ва агрономик усуллар шунингдек, “Ин витро” (шиша ичида) кўпайтириш ва биологик назорат тадбирлари таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар. Замонавий биотехнологиялар, картошка уруғчилиги, иқлим омиллари, генетик модификация усули (ГМУ), генетик-селекция, молекуляр маркерлаш, ўсимлик тўқима култураси, монодурагай, “Ин витро”.

**НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ И ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ
БИОТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СЕМЕНОВОДСТВЕ КАРТОФЕЛЯ**

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Аннотация. В статье освещены научно-методические и теоретические основы использования современных биотехнологий в семеноводстве картофеля. Изучены научные подходы к созданию новых сортов картофеля, свободных от вирусов и адаптированных к климатическим условиям, с использованием современных биотехнологических методов. Проведен анализ генетико-селекционных методов, молекулярной маркировки, культуры тканей растений, моноклонального разведения, микробиологических, экологических и агрономических подходов, а также методов «Ин витро» (в пробирке) размножения и биологического контроля.

Ключевые слова. Современные биотехнологии, семеноводство картофеля, климатические факторы, метод генетической модификации (ГММ), генетико-селекционные методы, молекулярная маркировка, культура тканей растений, моноклональное разведение, микробиологические, экологические и агрономические методы, методы «ин витро» размножения и мероприятия по биологическому контролю.

**SCIENTIFIC, METHODOLOGICAL AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF
MODERN BIOTECHNOLOGIES IN POTATO SEED PRODUCTION**

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Abstract. *The article highlights the scientific, methodological, and theoretical foundations of using modern biotechnologies in potato seed production. Scientific approaches to the development of new potato varieties that are virus-free and adapted to climatic conditions using advanced biotechnological methods are studied. An analysis is conducted on genetic selection methods, molecular marking, plant tissue culture, monoclonal propagation, microbiological, ecological, and agronomic approaches, as well as "in vitro" propagation techniques and biological control measures.*

Keywords. *Modern biotechnologies, potato seed production, climatic factors, genetic modification method (GMM), genetic selection methods, molecular marking, plant tissue culture, monoclonal propagation, microbiological, ecological, and agronomic methods, "in vitro" propagation techniques and biological control measures.*

INTRODUCTION.

Modern biotechnology serves to protect the environment and improve human living conditions. Biotechnology is a new branch of biological science, based on such applied sciences as genetics, molecular biology, microbiology, biochemistry, breeding methods and ecology. Today, the use of modern biotechnology in the cultivation of potatoes, the main food crop, allows to improve product quality and introduce a low-cost sustainable system. It also ensures economic efficiency in potato seed production.

Modern biotechnology is used in many areas, for example, using microbiological methods, biological suspensions, biological preparations and biopesticides are prepared for plant cultivation. Also, in breeding work, plant and animal cells are used to create new varieties of plants or breeds of animals that are resistant to various influences.

Today, agricultural methods are developing, and accordingly, innovative approaches, the use of new techniques and technologies, as well as the expansion of digitalization and artificial intelligence capabilities, are also relevant. It is necessary to organize the proper use of biochemical agents, especially to reduce the negative effects that may pose a threat to humans, plants and animals.

Based on this, many scientists recommend the effective use of beneficial microorganisms in ecological and agronomic practices in agriculture to increase soil fertility, and in plant cultivation. These practices are useful for the use of biological methods in genetically modified organisms, and for organizing the proper use of synthetic fertilizers and chemicals (pesticides, herbicides).

LITERATURE REVIEW.

Modern biotechnologies are grouped into food biotechnology, agricultural biotechnology, industrial biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, diagnostics, reagent biotechnology, biohydrometallurgy biotechnology, and environmental biotechnology [1]. In addition, modern biotechnologies can be used to assess the biological value of potatoes and determine the level of absorption of vitamins and minerals.

The formation of univalents and multivalents in various meiotic anomalies in the development of potato tubers, the presence of chromosomes in the form of bridges, triads, and polyads (with a positive characteristic) [2] also affect efficiency. However, if preparation for climate-specific changes is not carried out, biological processes in the soil will change negatively and the activity of beneficial microorganisms will be limited. In potato seed production, using the heredity and genetic properties of the variety, varieties resistant to adverse climate changes are created by transferring chromosomes or genes to another variety using various methods [3].

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According to Russian scientists N. Korchemnaya and others, countries such as China, Russia, Holland, USA, Germany and India have developed an effective science-based breeding system and are creating new intensive, high-yielding varieties [4]. Also, scientists such as V.P. Nagorskaya, A.V. Reunov, L.A. Lapshina, I.M. Ermak and A.O. Barabanova are conducting research on the mechanisms of cell interaction against viruses [5]. This study examined the possibilities of the natural environment in combating viruses.

Potato breeding research in Poland and Germany is gaining success. In particular, the Jessica, Lena, and Ania varieties are recognized as resistant to viral infections and high-yielding [6]. Belarusian breeders are using binary vectors in their research to express the specific antimicrobial peptides citropin-melitin in potatoes by the agrobacterial transformation method [7]. This method allows the production of peptides using viral proteins.

Also, the possibilities of micro-tuberculosis cultivation using the "In vitro" method are being expanded at the Changins-Vadensvil agroskopi Recherche research station in France [8]. At the research station (laboratory), the stages of growing micro-plants, propagating them in the form of mini-tuberculosis, and transforming them into a tuber are carried out on the basis of modern biotechnologies. In 2017, the growth and yield of potatoes fed with fish amino acids (FAA) were studied in Paju, South Korea [9]. The study found that the physical and chemical state of the soil improved, and microorganisms provided nutrients for plant growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

Food products, as well as the demand for potato products, vary from region to region depending on the methods of cultivation, processing, and consumption. Since plant cells are biologically and morphologically variable, genetic marking and varietal traits in potato seed production can help preserve the crop for a long time. Naturally, the plant cell wall protects it from mechanical stress and filters molecules entering and leaving the cell.

To restore or improve the function of plant tissues, new organisms are created with the fundamental properties of normal and pathological tissues for biological substitutes [10]. The functions and basic properties of plant cells are studied in the science of cytology, as well as in genetics and molecular biology.

With the help of breeding and biotechnology, changes in the genotype, morphology and physiology of plants can be made by transferring donor genotypes to elite varieties. In breeding, crops are divided into crops in nurseries, variety testing and propagation. Molecular marker technology is used to create new varieties through breeding, mutagenesis and genetic engineering methods. By correctly analyzing the genome and genes of plants, it is possible to increase their drought tolerance, increase their reproduction or carry out genetic modification.

Using modern biotechnologies, it is possible to grow new tissues by adapting plant tissues to each other. In the "in vitro" method, biological characteristics are enriched and, at the same time, resistance to various factors is achieved, while in potato seed breeding, specific characteristics are formed with biologically active substances.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION.

Organic production systems are important in agriculture. They are based not on the use of non-renewable resources, but on ecological processes, biodiversity, and cycles adapted to local

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conditions (tested). These approaches benefit the environment, are fair to all users, and ensure a good quality of life.

The use of modern production methods, innovative technologies, biotechnological methods, and developments in agriculture can yield positive results in increasing economic efficiency. In particular, Uzbekistan needs to improve the seed production system to reduce potato imports and provide the population with high-quality, disease-free potatoes. To do this, a priority-oriented and effective management system is needed, which provides for the gradual and impartial supply of high-quality potato seeds to potato growers. The implementation of this priority will be the adaptation of crops and farming systems to market requirements through modern biotechnologies.

The method of genetic modification (GMM), which is carried out on the basis of modern biotechnology, creates new varieties of potato varieties that are resistant to diseases and pests, as well as to climatic factors (based on genome analysis). The biological changes carried out help to form biometric data of potato varieties and identify genetic characteristics in the selection process [11]. Genetics can be considered the scientific and theoretical basis of selection in creating new varieties and hybrids of plants.

In many developed countries, these technological methods have already been included in breeding programs. At the same time, the use of molecular diagnostics prevents the spread of viruses and the consumption of virus-infected potatoes, reduces the costs of combating various dangerous infections by 15 to 30 percent. The costs of genetically modified varieties are reduced by 10 to 20 percent and increases profitability. According to world experience, GMO technologies help reduce crop losses by 15-20%. Some sources emphasize that food products grown using the GMO method can have an impact on the natural ecosystem, human health, and biological diversity [12].

In potato seed production, CRISPR-Cas9 (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats) technology is an effective technology for genetic engineering, which helps to increase the resistance of potato varieties to drought, viruses, and diseases. Also, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and (DNA) sequencing methods determine the effect of proteins and nucleic acids on potato seeds and their properties. This method allows studying the genetic modification of potatoes, immunity to viruses, and other biological properties.

The conclusions obtained as a result of the genetic mapping method accelerate the process of creating new potato varieties. The reason is that plant tolerance to drought conditions involves changes at the tissue, physiological and molecular levels. The main component of drought tolerance of a potato variety depends on the stability and integrity of the cell membrane. At the same time, molecular marker technology allows for early identification of certain characteristics of a potato variety. In addition, marker-based breeding technology expands genetic diversity in determining the adaptive characteristics and tolerance of a new variety.

This allows for the determination of plant resistance to various diseases and increased productivity. It allows for the creation of varieties and the renewal of adapted varieties by changing the main characteristics. As a result of mutations in genes in the potato genome, varieties can better adapt to the external environment and develop intensively.

In potato seed production, hybrid seed production improves disease resistance and tolerance to various climatic factors, and increases yield. In this method, the biological characteristics of hybrids are taken into account when implementing agrotechnical measures to increase yield [13]. Also, in potato seed production, beneficial genes are an important aspect of monohybrid breeding and increase the possibilities of creating varieties with new properties. Monohybrid breeding is the

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crossing of organisms that differ from each other in two pairs of alternative characters [14]. It should be noted that the method of planting seedlings (in the form of cuttings) is also widely used in breeding work. In this method, cuttings are prepared from disease-free, strong root tips and lateral shoots. Cuttings are 20-25 cm long, 3-6 cuttings are made from one plant and planted in special places and propagated [15].

Effective strategic objectives and preventive approaches to the spread and control of viral diseases in potatoes are important [16]. One of the main problems in potato seed production is the cultivation of seeds under viral conditions or early infection with viruses. Potatoes are more susceptible to viruses than other crops. Today, more than 50 types of potato viruses have been identified. The most common viruses are potato yellow spot virus, potato T virus, potato yellowing virus, potato leaf curl virus, potato Y virus, potato X virus and potato S virus.

These viruses are widespread in almost all countries and have a negative impact on potato yields [17]. The effect of viruses between varieties varies, and varieties that are less susceptible to the virus can become a source of virus transmission [18]. As mentioned above, the use of PCR methods to determine the presence or absence of viruses in a variety is quite effective. Viruses in potatoes are difficult to detect for a long time and their symptoms are quite difficult to recognize.

For example, viruses and the diseases they carry are rare in foothill conditions. At an altitude of 1200 m and above sea level, potato crops are rarely affected by viral and bacterial diseases. Such conditions are also true for potato seed production. Because virus-free potato seed production increases the yield by 20-50%. Today, the experience of planting microclonal tissues of high-quality potato varieties free of viruses using modern methods (in vitro) and propagating the resulting microoffspring as seeds is being developed. "In vitro" technologies allow studying the genetic structure of the population, quickly and accurately selecting potato seeds using molecular genetic markers and biochip technologies, which helps to effectively manage the selection process.

The tissues of plant root cells allow the growth of new roots, determining the quality of seeds and ensuring their development [19]. In world experience, innovative methods are being developed based on cell, chromosome and genetic engineering technologies. Many problems are being effectively solved by studying plant genes using genetic engineering. In potato seed production, taking into account these features, it is possible to ensure efficiency in seed production by using the "In vitro" method. "In vitro" cultivation accelerates selection work, increases the possibility of preparing perfect materials that are resistant to negative external influences, as well as genetically and morphologically homogeneous. In particular, the possibilities for conducting research on methods of tissue culture in laboratory conditions from virus-free potato varieties and the creation of new varieties have expanded. In many scientific laboratories in Uzbekistan, the development of virus-free potato seed production using the "In vitro" method is being launched. In this case, 3-stage micro and mini-germination is being established, and high-quality virus-free potato seeds are being prepared in a short time. Economic efficiency is achieved by reducing the time and resources required. In conclusion, there are opportunities in Uzbekistan to increase the economic efficiency of potato seed production by increasing the population's demand for potato consumption and mitigating the impact of various climatic factors, using modern biotechnologies based on foreign experience, as well as the achievements of biological engineering.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS.

In order to preserve the natural ecosystem in agriculture and increase productivity, it is necessary to use innovative technologies, as well as to protect it from the socio-economic and political-legal aspects. Namely, restoring land productivity, protecting rare species of animals and plants, preserving the gene pool, and effectively using genetic resources have a positive impact on food security.

In particular, in potato seed production, it is necessary to introduce modern biotechnologies, clearly determine costs, and consistently implement long-term strategic priorities. In conclusion, it is necessary to understand high-quality seeds and agricultural practices as a factor of economic efficiency in potato cultivation. Because high-quality potato seeds can reduce agro-technical costs and increase productivity by 20 to 50 percent.

As a result of the development of biotechnology, new scientific research and innovations are being created, which serve the economic interests of farmers as well as agricultural enterprises. Therefore, supporting the phased production of high-quality seeds by the "In vitro" method between scientific research institutions and potato growers ensures economic efficiency.

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